

Complete Stiffness Characterization of a Lamellar Metal/Ceramic Composite using Ultrasonic Spectroscopy Techniques

Siddhartha Roy ^a, Jörg-Martin Gebert ^b and Alexander Wanner ^c

Institut für Werkstoffkunde I, Universität Karlsruhe (TH)

Kaiserstr. 12, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

Siddhartha.roy@kit.edu ^a, joerg-martin.gebert@kit.edu ^b, Alexander.wanner@kit.edu ^c

SUMMARY

The elastic stiffness matrix of an orthotropic metal/ceramic composite produced by infiltration of a freeze-cast ceramic preform is examined. Two complementary ultrasonic spectroscopy methods were used to measure all nine independent elastic constants on a single sample. Consistent and reproducible results were obtained.

Keywords: Metal/ceramic composites, freeze-casting, non destructive testing, elastic analysis, ultrasonics

INTRODUCTION

Growing demands of aircraft and automobile industries have resulted into continuous search of new materials with light weight and improved structural properties. Composite materials were thus developed because no monolithic material could satisfy all the structural needs [1]. Typically, composite materials contain a reinforcement supported by a binder (matrix) material. As the name suggests, the matrix material in metal matrix composites (MMC) is a metallic material (pure metal or an alloy) while the reinforcement is mostly a ceramic. MMCs offer several advantages in comparison to unreinforced metals and better known composites such as polymer matrix composites (PMC). Advantages over unreinforced metals include higher specific stiffness and strength, better dimensional stability, much improved creep and fatigue resistance etc. With respect to PMCs, MMCs offer higher strength, stiffness and conductivity (both thermal and electrical), higher operating temperatures, better transverse properties etc [2]. A new possibility to fabricate metal/ceramic composites has recently been opened by the availability of ceramic preforms processed by freeze-casting [3, 4, 5] of ceramic suspensions. Preforms produced this way show a hierarchical domain structure and have excellent permeability for liquids and gases along with acceptable mechanical strengths. Thus they are suitable for the fabrication of metal/ceramic composites by infiltration of liquid metal [3, 6].

To predict the off-axis loading behavior of an anisotropic material, knowledge of the complete stiffness tensor is a must. The generalized Hooke's law for an anisotropic material is written as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \cdot \varepsilon_{kl} \quad (1)$$

where C_{ijkl} is the stiffness tensor while the terms σ_{ij} and ε_{kl} are the stress and strain tensors, respectively. Both stress and strain tensors are 2nd order tensors (having 9 terms in each) and the stiffness tensor is 4th order tensor having 81 terms. However, because of symmetry conditions, ($C_{ijkl} = C_{ijlk}$ and $C_{ijkl} = C_{jikl}$) the number of elastic constants are reduced to 36 instead of 81 [7] and the stiffness tensor can be expressed by a 6 x 6 stiffness matrix. Furthermore, strain energy considerations of a crystal show that this matrix is symmetric, i.e. $C_{ij}=C_{ji}$. This reduces the number of independent elastic constants to 21 in the most anisotropic triclinic system. A particular crystal symmetry or atomic arrangement can further reduce the number of independent elastic constants so that a material with orthotropic symmetry has 9 independent elastic constants. The stiffness matrix of an orthotropic material is written as:

$$C_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In the stiffness matrix of Equation (2) the diagonal elements C_{ii} with ($i=1-3$) are the longitudinal elastic constants, the diagonal elements with ($i=4-6$) are the shear elastic constants while the non-zero off diagonal elements are the elastic constants for extension-extension coupling, respectively.

Our previous work had concentrated on the various mechanical aspects of individual domains (elastic anisotropy [8, 9], elastic-plastic anisotropy [10, 11], processing induced thermal residual stress [12] and internal load transfer under external compressive load along freezing direction [13]). The aim of this work is to determine the complete stiffness matrix of a poly-domain sample non-destructively using ultrasonic techniques.

MEASUREMENT PRINCIPLE

Two complementary non-destructive techniques, ultrasound phase spectroscopy (UPS) and resonant ultrasound spectroscopy (RUS) were used in this work. In the following the fundamentals of these two techniques are briefly described.

Ultrasound Phase Spectroscopy (UPS)

UPS is an ideal method to determine sound velocities in samples exhibiting large attenuations due to scattering and internal frictions, where better known pulse propagation methods fare poorly. In UPS, continuous and sinusoidal elastic waves are passed through the sample and the phase shift is measured as a function of frequency [14, 15].

A plane monochromatic wave propagating un-damped in the x-direction can be written as:

$$u(x,t) = u_0 \cdot e^{i(\omega t + kx)} \quad (3)$$

where $(\omega t + kx)$ is the phase function, $(\omega = 2\pi f)$ is the circular frequency and $(k_w = 2\pi/\lambda)$ is the wave number. For a specimen of length L_s , the group velocity of a pulse (A pulse being a superposition of many waves) is defined as:

$$V_g = -\frac{2\pi L_s}{(d\Delta\phi/df)}. \quad (4)$$

The denominator on the right hand side of Equation (4) is the slope of the phase-frequency plot. Hence, group velocity is determined by increasing the phase in the specimen by increasing the frequency and then finding the slope of the phase–frequency plot. If the plot turns out to be a straight line with a constant slope within a region of frequency, it suggests that the material is non-dispersive in that region. Once V_g for a particular mode (longitudinal or shear with appropriate propagation and polarizations vectors) of wave propagation is determined, the corresponding elastic constant C_{ii} is determined according to:

$$C_{ii} = \rho V_g^2. \quad (5)$$

In Equation (5), ρ is the density, $(i=1-3)$ refers to longitudinal elastic constants while $(i=4-6)$ corresponds to shear elastic constants.

Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy (RUS)

RUS involves the study of the eigenfrequencies of solids. These frequencies depend upon the shape, elastic constants, crystallographic orientation or texture, density and dissipation properties of the body. Hence, with this technique the complete stiffness matrix of any single sample with relatively low symmetry can be obtained non-destructively by measuring its eigenfrequencies [16, 17]. The sample whose elastic constants are to be measured is held lightly between two piezoelectric transducers to ensure a free oscillation of the sample. One transducer applies a sinusoidal excitement to some point on the sample and its resonance response is measured at some other point by the second transducer. A large response is observed when the frequency of the driving transducer corresponds to one of the sample eigenfrequencies. This procedure is repeated for many frequencies over a large range. Essential to the successful implementation of RUS is the ability to determine the eigenfrequencies of a body from its shape, density and elastic constants (known as forward or direct problem). Once these are computed, carefully constructed fitting procedures are used to find the moduli from the measured frequencies (known as backward or inverse problem). The procedure to solve the direct problem is mathematically complicated and its thorough description is outside the scope this work. A rigorous analysis of this problem as well as the computer algorithm used almost universally is described in detail in the book written by Migliori and Sarrao [18]. However, the task of computing elastic moduli analytically from the eigenfrequencies has never been undertaken successfully. Instead, a nonlinear optimization procedure has been established. This procedure yields a set of parameters that produces resonance frequencies that are in the best possible agreement with the measured spectra. In order to determine the best possible parameters, a figure of merit, *FOM* is constructed, which provides a measure of how well the calculated and measured resonance frequencies agree. The *FOM* is defined as:

$$FOM = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} w_i \cdot (f_{calc} - f_{mea})^2 \quad (6)$$

where f_{calc} and f_{mea} are the calculated and the measured eigenfrequencies respectively, w_i is a weighting factor chosen based on the confidence of the experimenter for the particular frequency and N_p is the number of resonant frequencies. In the present work, this weighting factor was kept as unity for all the resonant frequencies. As several eigenfrequencies depend in almost identical way on some of the elastic constants, hence many more resonances than the total number of parameters to be fit must be measured for a meaningful analysis. Migliori and Sarrao [18] suggest that the number of resonant frequencies measured should be at least 5 times and preferably 8–10 times the number of parameters to be determined. Furthermore, the sample for RUS must have very well defined geometry with face parallelism a few microns per mm and excellent face perpendicularity. Above conditions being fulfilled and using a reasonably good guess for the input parameters, the error bars for compressional moduli in the range of 0.5–1.0%, for shear moduli in the range of 0.02% and for off-diagonal moduli in the range of 2–3% are achievable.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen material

Alumina preforms with porosities of about 56 vol. % were produced at Institut für Keramik im Maschinenbau (IKM) at Universität Karlsruhe, Karlsruhe, Germany, via freeze-casting of a ceramic suspension, freeze-drying and subsequent sintering [19]. The preform used for the composite studied in this work was fabricated from a suspension having 22 vol% alumina powders and it was freeze cast at -30 °C. Preforms with

Figure 1: Typical optical micrographs of the poly domain composite sample; (a) microstructure of the face perpendicular to the freezing direction, (b) microstructure of a face parallel to the freezing direction and (c) schematic diagram for a poly domain sample with direction 1 being the freezing direction

nominal dimensions of 10×44×66 mm³ were infiltrated with a eutectic aluminium–silicon alloy (Al–12Si) at the Institute of Surface Technology and Materials Science at Aalen University of Applied Sciences, Germany, using a squeeze casting technique. For ultrasonic analysis, one rectangular parallelepiped sample was cut from the composite

block and all faces of the sample were polished with SiC emery paper until plane parallelism down to few microns was attained. The optical micrograph of Figure 1a shows the typical microstructure of the face perpendicular to the freezing direction while Figure 1b shows the micrograph of a face parallel to the freezing direction. In these optical micrographs the ceramic component is dark while the metallic alloy is brighter. Figure 1c shows the schematic structure of a poly domain composite sample with direction 1 being the freezing direction. The dimensions of the sample parallel to the 1, 2 and 3 directions in Figure 1c were 5.221 ± 0.008 mm, 5.439 ± 0.003 mm and 5.897 ± 0.012 mm respectively and its mass was 0.54033 g.

UPS

The measurements were accomplished using an electronic network analyser (Advantest, model R3754A) and two identical broadband ultrasonic transducers (Panametrics, model V122 with nominal central frequency 7.5 MHz and diameter 9.5 mm for longitudinal elastic constants and model V155 with nominal central frequency 5 MHz and diameter 12.7 mm for shear elastic constants). These transducers were attached on opposite sides of the rectangular parallelepiped samples using a water soluble couplant. For longitudinal elastic constants, the phase and amplitude spectra were recorded in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 15 MHz; while for shear elastic constants the same range was from 10 kHz to 10 MHz. Six different measurements were carried out for the three shear elastic constants (a combination of two different measurements for each shear elastic constant and the average of these two velocities was further used to determine the shear elastic constant). Figure 2a shows the experimental setup used for UPS. The network analyser is seen in the background.

Figure 2: Experimental setups for a) UPS and b) RUS

RUS

For RUS, a sample was placed along its body diagonal between two identical transducers attached to a very rigid stage. The complete stage along with the transducers was manufactured by Quasar (Quasar International Inc., New Mexico, USA). The same network analyzer used for UPS was used to generate the input signal and to record the output signal. A wideband, high speed amplifier (model BA4825 from NF Corporation, Yokohama, Japan) was used to amplify the signal to the input transducer. Phase and

amplitude were measured for each swept frequency. Resonant frequencies were determined from the amplitude spectra. At least four measurements were carried out with different body diagonals of the sample being in touch with the transducers. This ensured that none of the resonant frequencies was missed. Resonant frequencies for each measurement were determined and the averages of these values were put as input to back calculate the elastic constants based on the input values of the elastic constants and sample mass and dimensions. Figure 2b shows the experimental setup for RUS

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Typical phase and amplitude spectra obtained from the UPS of the actual composite sample using longitudinal transducers are shown in Figure 3. In the shown spectra, the

Figure 3: Typical phase and amplitude spectra obtained from the UPS test of the actual composite sample using a) longitudinal transducers and b) shear transducers

slope of the phase spectrum is constant over the complete frequency range for the measurement with longitudinal transducers while for the measurement with shear transducers the slope is constant over the frequency range limited by the arrows. In general, the slope of the phase spectrum was found to be fairly constant over a considerable frequency range for all of the measurements. This indicates that the velocity is in fact independent of frequency (absence of dispersion) and suggests that elastic constants computed based on the ultrasonic velocities can be assumed to be valid also under static loading conditions. From the slopes of the phase spectra the sound velocities were determined using Equation (4). Each measurement was repeated three times and the resulting velocities were reproducible. The average of these three velocities was used to determine the elastic constant using Equation (5).

Table 1: Average of the sound velocities determined from UPS and elastic constants calculated there from

Elastic constants	Sound velocity (m.s^{-1})	Value of elastic constants (GPa)
C_{11}	8657 ± 30	242 ± 2
C_{22}	7621 ± 4	187 ± 0
C_{33}	8141 ± 71	214 ± 3
C_{44}	4416 ± 94	64 ± 3
C_{55}	4834 ± 121	76 ± 4
C_{66}	4326 ± 112	61 ± 3

For RUS, the sample was assumed to have orthotropic symmetry, having 9 independent elastic constants. The three longitudinal and three shear elastic constants determined by UPS were used as input for RUS. However, with UPS it was not possible to determine the three off-diagonal stiffness constants without cutting the sample and hence initial guesses were made for them based on the theory of uni-directional fiber reinforced composites and using the literature values for the stiffnesses of alumina and Al-12Si and calculating the ceramic content from the measured density and assuming no porosity. These stiffness constants as well as the sample dimensions and mass were put as input in the code developed by Migliori and Sarrao [18]. A first run of the code predicted that the first 90 resonant frequencies should be present within the frequency range of 0.3 MHz to 1.4 MHz. This frequency range was swept in small steps with a step width of 10 Hz and sweep time of 50 milliseconds. Figure 4 shows the amplitude spectrum obtained from RUS of a poly domain sample of Composite Type B. Resonant frequencies were determined from the peaks of the amplitude spectrum. According to

Figure 4: Amplitude spectra obtained from a poly domain composite sample

Migliori and Sarrao [18], the number of fitted resonant frequencies should be 5–10 times the number of elastic constants to be determined. As orthotropic symmetry was assumed for the sample, it had 9 independent elastic constants and hence 50–90 resonant frequencies were fitted. Table 2 shows the result obtained by fitting the experimentally measured resonant frequencies to the code written by Migliori and Sarrao [18] based on the input values of the elastic constants and sample mass and dimensions. Fit obtained for first 40 resonant frequencies are shown here, although more resonant frequencies were considered. The column headers in Table 2 have the following meanings: n corresponds to the number of the mode, f_{ex} and f_r are the measured and the fitted frequencies respectively (in MHz) and $\%err$ is the error in fitting that particular mode. Table 3 shows the elastic constants obtained from RUS for various numbers of fitted resonant frequencies ranging from 50–90. The first row also lists the input values of the respective elastic constants. As has already been mentioned, input values of the longitudinal (C_{11} , C_{22} and C_{33}) and the shear (C_{44} , C_{55} and C_{66})

elastic constants were determined by UPS on the same sample. Input values of the three remaining elastic constants (C_{12} , C_{13} and C_{23}) were determined based on the theoretical UD fiber model calculations. Deviations of the fitted elastic constants from the input values are also

Table 2: Comparison between experimentally obtained and fitted frequencies for the first 40 resonant peaks obtained from RUS on a poly domain sample

n	fex (MHz)	fr (MHz)	%err	n	fex (MHz)	fr (MHz)	%err
1	0.349025	0.347033	-0.57	21	0.725113	0.724274	-0.12
2	0.400843	0.403743	0.72	22	0.73134	0.72658	-0.65
3	0.462155	0.463939	0.39	23	0.751175	0.752197	0.14
4	0.480615	0.481898	0.27	24	0.756433	0.752693	-0.49
5	0.483008	0.489053	1.25	25	0.763857	0.756511	-0.96
6	0.507935	0.515612	1.51	26	0.768457	0.768816	0.05
7	0.528040	0.524268	-0.71	27	0.780653	0.784899	0.54
8	0.540227	0.535400	-0.89	28	0.804338	0.795677	-1.08
9	0.542548	0.540400	-0.40	29	0.82403	0.830846	0.83
10	0.572800	0.567331	-0.95	30	0.871038	0.870795	-0.03
11	0.591845	0.590179	-0.28	31	0.890303	0.890195	-0.01
12	0.594373	0.593917	-0.08	32	0.893818	0.893176	-0.07
13	0.614453	0.614438	0.00	33	0.902815	0.90696	0.46
14	0.629977	0.626010	-0.63	34	0.907295	0.908284	0.11
15	0.637033	0.637101	0.01	35	0.910995	0.9119	0.1
16	0.661293	0.668026	1.02	36	0.921683	0.929716	0.87
17	0.690370	0.688507	-0.27	37	0.946545	0.949751	0.34
18	0.694400	0.690852	-0.51	38	0.961253	0.955681	-0.58
19	0.699050	0.695410	-0.52	39	0.962803	0.961457	-0.14
20	0.717398	0.722718	0.74	40	0.968985	0.978338	0.97

Table 3: Summary of the elastic constants obtained from RUS for various numbers of fitted modes and their comparison with elastic constants measured via UPS

	RMS error (%)	C_{11} (GPa)	C_{22} (GPa)	C_{33} (GPa)	C_{23} (GPa)	C_{13} (GPa)	C_{12} (GPa)	C_{44} (GPa)	C_{55} (GPa)	C_{66} (GPa)
Input	-	242	188	214	90	85	85	64	76	61
RUS50	0.58	257	200	203	79	65	90	62	74	65
Dev50		6%	6%	5%	14%	24%	6%	3%	3%	7%
RUS60	0.67	256	201	196	73	57	90	62	74	65
Dev60		6%	7%	8%	19%	33%	6%	3%	3%	7%
RUS70	0.77	255	201	194	72	54	89	62	74	66
Dev70		5%	7%	9%	20%	36%	5%	3%	3%	8%
RUS80	0.92	257	200	200	76	60	89	62	75	66
Dev80		6%	6%	7%	16%	29%	5%	3%	1%	8%
RUS90	1	258	200	198	75	57	91	61	76	65
Dev90		7%	6%	7%	17%	33%	7%	5%	0%	7%

shown in the same table. It is clearly observed from Table 3 that in all cases the elastic constants determined by UPS show very good reproducibility also in RUS (deviations lying in the range of 6-7%). On the contrary, the elastic constants whose values were guessed based on the fiber model show large deviation. The RMS error increases from 0.5825% for 50 fitted resonant frequencies to about 1% for 90 fitted resonant frequencies. Although this increase in RMS error suggests a worsening of the quality of the fit, the confidence level for 90 fitted resonant frequencies is much higher because of the use of almost double the number of fitted frequencies. These RMS errors lie in the same range already observed for composites reinforced by particulate reinforcements (isotropic symmetry) [20] and by fiber reinforcements (transverse isotropic symmetry) [21]. The value of the RMS error is considerably higher than that suggested by Migliori and Sarrao [18] (they suggest a value in the range of 0.1-0.2% for a very good measurement with a very well prepared sample). This relatively high RMS error may be attributed to the difficulty in preparation of a sample with very precise geometry, to inhomogeneities inherent in the composite sample used, and to the inability to obtain good initial guesses for the off diagonal elastic constants.

This knowledge of the complete stiffness matrix is essential to simulate the off-axis loading behavior of the material and to estimate the Young's modulus along any direction in space. Figure 5 shows the 3D plot of Young's modulus for the composite under study computed from the RUS fit for 50 resonant peaks. The calculations were carried out in MATLAB, using the expression proposed by Nye [7].

Figure 5: 3D plot of Young's modulus. Direction 1 is the freezing direction

CONCLUSIONS

Complete stiffness matrix of a novel metal/ceramic composite having lamellar interpenetrating structure was determined. The sample was assumed to have orthotropic symmetry. Three longitudinal and three shear elastic constants of the sample were first determined by ultrasound phase spectroscopy. These measured elastic constants were further used to determine the complete stiffness matrix by resonant ultrasound spectroscopy. Excellent match was obtained between the elastic constants determined by the two ultrasonic spectroscopic techniques. Knowledge of the complete stiffness matrix was used to plot the 3D distribution of the Young's modulus.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank M.J. Hoffmann, R. Oberacker, and T. Waschgies of Insitut für Keramik im Maschinenbau, Universität Karlsruhe, as well as A. Nagel and co-workers at Aalen University of Applied Sciences, Germany, for providing the specimen material. Financial support from Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Bonn, Germany under project Wa1122/3-1 is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. ASM International Handbook Committee, "Engineered materials handbook, vol. 1, Composites", ASM International, 1987.
2. Chawla N., Chawla K. K., "Metal Matrix Composites", Springer, 2006
3. Mattern A., "Interpenetrierende Metall-Keramik-Verbundwerkstoffe mit isotropen und anisotropen Al₂O₃-Verstärkungen", Doctoral Thesis (in German), Universität Karlsruhe (TH), Karlsruhe, Germany. Full text appeared in: Schriftenreihe des Instituts für Keramik im Maschinenbau, 2005, ISSN 1436-3488, vol. 44
4. Sofie S. W., Dogan F., *J Am Ceram Soc*, 2001, 84(7) : 1459–64
5. Fukasawa T., Ando M., Ohji T., Kanzaki S., *J Am Ceram Soc*, 2001, 84(1): 230–2
6. Deville S., Saiz E., Nalla R. K., Tomsia A. P., *Science*, 2006, 311 : 515–8
7. Nye, J. F., "Physical Properties of Crystals", Oxford Science Publications, 1985
8. Roy, S., Wanner, A., *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2008, 68 : 1136-1143,
9. Ziegler, T., Neubrand, A., Roy, S., Wanner, A., Piat, R., *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2009, 69: 620-626
10. Roy, S., Butz, B., Wanner, A., *13th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM13)*, Stockholm, Sweden, June 2-5, 2008, paper no. 0303,
11. Roy, S., Butz, B., Wanner, A., *Acta Materialia*, communicated
12. Roy, S., Gibmeier, J., Wanner, A., *Powder Diffraction Journal*, accepted
13. Roy, S., Gibmeier, J., Wanner, A., *Adv. Engg. Mater.*, accepted
14. Lynnworth, L. C., Papadakis, E. P., Rea, W. R., "Ultrasonic measurement of phase and group velocity using continuous wave transmission techniques", *AMMRC Report CTR 73–2*, January 1973
15. Wanner, A., *Mater. Sci. and Engg.*, 1998, A248: 35–43.
16. Sarrao, J. L., Chen, S. R., Visscher, W. M., Lei, M., Kocks, U. F., Migliori, A., *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 1994,65: 2139 – 2140
17. Leisure, R. G., Wills, F. A., *Journal of Physics - Condensed Matter*, 1997,9: 6001 – 6029, 1997
18. Migliori, A., Sarrao, J. L., *Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy: Applications to Physics, Materials Measurements and Nondestructive Evaluation*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1997
19. Waschgies, T., Oberacker, R., Hoffmann, M. J., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2009, 92[S1]: S79-S84
20. Koopman, M., Chawla, K.K., Coffin, C., Patterson, B. R., Deng, X., Patel, B. V., Fang, Z., Lockwood, G., *Adv. Engg. Mater.*, 2002, 4: 37 – 42, 2002
21. Vuorinen, J.E., Schwarz, R. B., McCullough, C., *J. Acc. Soc. Am.*, 108, 574 – 579, 2000